

THROUGH THE USE OF ENERGY SAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PRODUCTION OF THERMAL ENERGY TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE

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Summary

Re - renewable energy sources in this article require the use of actual istochnikov ministry sources , the use of solar energy as well as the environment against the effects of the situation was. In addition to the wide solar air heater in faen in dostup now ,if cancer has spread, the spread used and used main types, working principles and their advantages, as well as the theoretical analysis of its shortcomings is presented. Also, the analysis on the basis of solar air heater is a new type of offer did not.

Key words: *energy, Solar air heater, air flow, heat exchange, channel, dust absorbing, insulating, transparent surface, corps.*

Today's the day many researchers and scientists in the heat supply system in the energy and fuel and energy resources for the effective and efficient use of the opportunity that gives you the advanced technology and equipment introduce you to on scientific research from the get go. As it is known, in today's day in industrial scale used natural fuel, energy resources are drastically reduced and has been, the same reason for re - renewable energy from the use of natural resources and the environmental situation of the existing levels,though keep to satxiberadi [1], because 21century, the world energy in the field, two important problems face came. sector: reliable energy supply, ensure and

Emerging environmental issues, on one hand, the energy of the source is extremely unstable in the market, the other on the other hand, the energy supply system in dangers, if only from fuel use on the basis of built is, every kind from the source of that went away resources into account taking without. ends, this is the future in serious consequences lead lead can [2]

Various different energy sources, use of global economic development and in sanoatlashtirish an important role plays. Present at the time of the solar energy sustainable development in the process increasingly growing growing energy needs meet to important energy source is, because this energy is unlimited and clean energy source is. [3]

Present at the time the most expensive energy of the types one of this heat energy. For this reason, that is, heat energy use in and out of

out of itself to specific difficulty they come, it's as a result of the fuel price of constant growth, thermal power stations effective decrease, the consumer heat with providing in the process of their effectiveness about 40-70% to up makes. [4-9].

Solar air heater studying the first category is "its in channel flow configurations on classification" is. This category four, the same configuration is.

The air flow channel configurations of solar air heater efficiency and the collector from which flows the air temperature, the effect of the significant amount since the reason, the researchers of each different type of air flow channel configurations understood that

[10]

The sun energy from the use of on many of the recommendations worked out are being. Solar energy collector of useful work ratio, the following formula on this is.

$$k = \frac{Q}{E_k * A}$$

Here: SP – the heat output of the collector, W/hours; the amount of solar energy that falls on the surface of 1 m² solar air heater solar air heater absorbering of the surface area, m². You can sp value, you can determine the flow of cooling water m, kg / s; according to him, specific heat capacity, Sp, W / hours/ (kg s) and out into the cooling water and the temperature difference in appointing the result

$$K_k = MS_r(T_2 - T_1)$$

Solar energy coefficient of the collector aspect ratio of the useful work and heat loss coefficient from its optical kk useful work through follows write you can:

$$k = \frac{K_k(t_1 - t_{\text{external}})}{i_k}$$

This here: ik – solar air heater, the solar energy that falls on the surface of flow intensity; W/m², kk-heat loss coefficient (W/m² in the above formula, a value of the ratio of useful work given instant, is given as the average of this value can be taken.the hours. However, the intensity of the flow of solar energy during the day to a maximum varies from scratch. As you can see, the ratio of useful work will be less than the maximum value of the average daily value.

In this device, as well as isitiladigan air drainage tubes are (1) to the center of the solar air heater is moved upwardly from the center of width and height is set to air because isitiladigan. [9] transparent window (2) solar air heater on the top is set and the window and diapers izolyasion the material with will be attached. Collector job, the camera H1 \ u003d 1 mm absorber thickness tarnished metal (3) is inserted into and triangular shape has, which konkav channels (4) in his work the surface of the surface

chess boards in the form of a set. The device in the air, take up to (5) and air exhaust pipes are there. Solar air heater corps (6) plastic on able, her inner part gözeneklidir. Absorber and the device housing between (fi please. 9) heat insulator of the material placed, they united to reference the insulation material (penaplast) (7) $h_2=2$ mm thick and the falls (8) $H_3=2,5$ mm thick

1-isitiladigan of exhaust air tubes are 2oyna, 3-tarnished metal surface (absorber), 4-channel a thorough, 6-corps, 7-linking insulation layer (penaplast), 8-falls.

Recommended by the solar air heater advantages.

This sunny weather heater advantages the following consists of.

1. Eka triangular shaped channels chess set as a result of solar air heater working surface and the channel of the inner and outer surface across the heat exchange process to occur will.

2. Triangular shaped air channel given convective geometric shape the air into as a result of the air in an intuitive action generated is , and the heat transfer process is accelerated.

3. Triangular shaped eka with air channel chess set as a result of the general triangular kanalli collector than less pressure loss.

4. Each a channel for this solar air heater installed air reception to readers particular installation as a result of air collector entire working surface across is moved.

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